

Parallel detection of okadaic acid and saxitoxin in mussels with an electrochemical aptamer-based assay

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ABSTRACT

Phycotoxins are highly toxic compounds bioaccumulating in marine organisms, thus seriously affecting human health. Two electrochemical aptasensors for parallel detection of okadaic acid (OA) and saxitoxin (STX), exploiting a competitive strategy, are then proposed in this study. Screen-printed electrochemical cells were modified first by the electrodeposition of gold nanoparticles and then by the electropolymerization of poly (aniline-co-anthranilic acid) copolymer or poly(L-lysine) film. A conjugate between bovine serum albumin and each phycotoxin was immobilized covalently on the polymeric film and competed with the free phycotoxin in solution for the binding with a specific biotinylated aptamer. The competition was traced with an enzymatic conjugate between streptavidin and alkaline phosphatase: upon addition of 1-naphthyl phosphate, the enzymatic conversion of the substrate occurred. Differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) measurements were carried out to detect the enzymatic product 1-naphthol. A signal-off response was retrieved with detection limits of 66.4 pg/mL for OA and 7.9 pg/mL for STX, respectively. The aptasensors were also tested in the analysis of real mussel samples and their performance was compared with those of commercial enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays. The developed sensing strategy offers an efficient approach for monitoring OA and STX in seafood, thus representing a significant step towards ensuring consumer safety.

1. Introduction

Coastal marine ecosystems are increasingly affected by harmful algal blooms (HABs), phenomena caused by blooms of microscopic algae or phytoplankton, including certain cyanobacteria (blue-green algae). Although the term also applies to harmful blooms of macroalgae (*i.e.*, seaweeds), HAB events are typically associated with a rapid proliferation and/or accumulation of toxic or otherwise noxious microalgae [1]. Thus, seawater quality can be worldwide affected by HABs, as several types of toxic substances are being released during these processes.

Phycotoxins are complex chemicals produced by eukaryotic and prokaryotic algal secondary metabolic pathways mainly as a defense response to predators, competitors or parasites. These metabolites are often harmless for the producer but may be toxic to either one or many members of the marine food web (as phytoplankton serves also as food for mollusks, like clams, oysters, and shellfish larvae) through filtering mechanisms. In humans, toxicity is caused through the impact of natural phycotoxins *via* various exposure routes including inhalation, direct skin

contact and, primarily, the consumption of contaminated seafood, in which the phycotoxins tend to accumulate due to multiple ingestion of algae by marine organisms. Toxins accumulated in seafood tissues can remain for considerable lengths of time after the bloom has declined in the seawater [2,3].

The exerted effects on human health are often severe, and are generally addressed as shellfish poisoning, a group of four syndromes (amnesic shellfish poisoning – ASP, diarrhetic shellfish poisoning – DSP, neurotoxic shellfish poisoning – NSP, paralytic shellfish poisoning – PSP), primarily associated to bivalve mollusks, that share some common features. DSP mainly manifests as diarrhea, with abdominal pain, nausea and vomiting that may also occur, and is caused by okadaic acid (OA), which inhibits intestinal cellular dephosphorylation. Prolonged consumption can induce the promotion of tumors of the gastrointestinal tract [4]. In addition to the just-mentioned symptoms, PSP may manifest with paresthesia (*e.g.*, tingling or burning body or skin parts), shortness of breath, dry mouth, confused or slurred speech, loss of coordination, *etc.* PSP is mainly caused by saxitoxin (STX) and its analogues, which act

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as selective and reversible, voltage-gated sodium channel blockers, preventing normal cellular functions. In cases of severe intoxication, PSP leads to respiratory paralysis and even death [5]. The acceptable levels of these toxins are 160 µg/kg and 800 µg/kg of shellfish meat for OA and STX, respectively [6,7]. As even such a small amount can lead to death, it is of outstanding importance to control the presence of algae and monitor the purity of the waters, as well as to control marine organisms intended for human consumption.

Various analytical methods have been developed over the years for phycotoxins analysis, the first of which was the *in vivo* mouse bioassay, considered as the standard quantitative method until 2011; then, advancements in science and technology gave rise to lab-based techniques alleviating costly animal maintenance and ethical issues [8]. Nowadays, traditional methods like chromatographic techniques, mass spectrometry and biological assays are used by certified laboratories for phycotoxins monitoring; however, these techniques often require time-consuming and complicated pretreatment procedures, together with sophisticated and expensive laboratory equipment to be performed. In addition, the lack of portability makes such techniques not suitable for *in situ* monitoring and, in general, for commercial, daily analyses. On the other hand, biosensors can be easily miniaturized to allow simple and real-time phycotoxin analysis with lower cost and at low levels [9]. Whether based on antibodies or aptamers, affinity-based biosensors have gained much attention; specifically, DNA-based ones have shown great progresses, providing accurate, specific and sensitive detection, including the advantages of improved stability and no batch-to-batch variability of synthetic oligonucleotides over antibodies [10–15]. Furthermore, aptamers own the versatility to be used either in a label-free modality – given the conformational change they undergo after target binding – or, upon sequence labelling, for a direct electrochemical or optical detection [16].

Electrochemical methods have been gaining increased popularity due to their compatibility with current sensor trends, such as device miniaturization, potential for point-of-care analysis, low cost, ease of implementation, together with high sensitivity and selectivity. In the past years, OA and STX had been widely detected by means of both simple or more structured aptamer-based electrochemical approaches, exploiting voltammetric [17–20], potentiometric [21] or field-effect [22,23] techniques for the detection [24]: however, as far as screen-printed technology is concerned, just a few of them were developed on low-cost, easily-modifiable and disposable electrochemical cells. Zeng and coworkers [25] developed a simple aptasensing strategy on screen-printed carbon electrodes modified with chitosan and gold nanoparticles, where a thiolated anti-OA aptamer was immobilized *via* self-assembly. Upon binding of the aptamer with OA, the electrochemical signal of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{-4/-3}$ redox probe increased, due to a

facilitated charge transfer in the system. OA was detected in the range 0.01–100 ng/mL with a detection limit of 6.7 pg/mL in standard solution and in real mussel and scallop samples. Rhouati et al. [26] proposed an electrochemical aptasensor with a similar detection strategy for multiple cyanotoxins, including OA and STX, on a disposable electrical printed microarray. The microarray was composed of eight individually addressable gold nanoparticles-modified carbon electrodes, each one bearing an aptamer dedicated to one toxin. The signal of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{-4/-3}$ redox probe increased upon the binding of the toxins in the range 0.018–200 nM, with a detection limit of 4.8 pM (≈ 3.9 pg/mL) for OA and 5.3 pM (≈ 1.6 pg/mL) for STX, respectively. Despite the low detection limits attained in both cases, the first approach foresees a quite time-consuming pretreatment procedure, while the second one was applied only in water samples. The above-mentioned studies are summarized in Table 1.

Indeed, the focus of our research was to develop a rapid, sensitive and selective biosensing strategy to detect in parallel target marine toxins like OA and STX in seafood. For this purpose, we used miniaturized screen-printed carbon electrodes modified with gold nanoparticles and a polymer (poly(aniline-co-anthranilic) or poly(L-lysine)) to improve their conductive features. Then, enzyme-linked aptamer assays were developed based on a competitive format: a conjugate between bovine serum albumin and OA (OA-BSA) or STX (STX-BSA) was covalently immobilized on the surface of the aforementioned electrochemical cells. To the best of our knowledge, none of the previously published studies on marine toxins detection made use of a toxin-BSA conjugate in a competitive format: the only exception consists of two immunoassays developed on 96-wells plates [27,28]. As small molecules are usually detected by techniques relying on a competitive format, the conjugation of the analyte with carrier proteins is thus widely used to promote these competition mechanisms. In fact, the use of carrier proteins can improve target accessibility, by providing spatial distribution, minimizing steric hindrance and promoting aptamer binding *via* conformation-dependent molecular recognition, which is critical for small-molecule sensing systems [29]. Moreover, carrier proteins may also simplify the immobilization of the targets on the sensing surface, making the related protocol compatible with conventional protein coupling strategies. Accordingly, our research group had successfully adopted this strategy in the electrochemical detection of aflatoxin B₁ [30]: pushed by the results obtained in this previous study, we decided to assess the versatility of the developed assay by testing it in the detection of toxins belonging to completely different classes compared to mycotoxins. Therefore, OA or STX solutions at different concentrations, containing an appropriate and fixed amount of a biotinylated aptamer (*i.e.*, a different one for each toxin, selected from libraries of aptamers as those with the highest affinity and specificity for OA [31,32]

Table 1
Electrochemical aptasensors for okadaic acid (OA) and saxitoxin (STX) detection.

Toxin	Platform	Technique	LOD (pg/mL)	DR (pg/mL)	Assay time (min)	Real sample	Ref.
Okadaic acid	C ₃ N ₄ /GCE	DPV	8×10^{-2}	8×10^{-2} –80.50	N.A.	Mussel	[17]
	THMS-DNA/PAH/sw	Potentiometry	24.2	40.3 – 8.1×10^4	80 + 27 min/channel	Shellfish	[21]
	AuNPs/CS/SPCE	CV	6.7	10 – 10^5	60	Mussel, scallop	[25]
	AuNPs/CE	SWV	3.9	14.5 – 1.6×10^5	20	Water	[26]
	OA-BSA/pLL/AuNPs/GSPE	DPV	66.4	0.1–80	85 + 250 s/channel	Mussel	This work
Saxitoxin	AgNPs/GCE	DPV	3×10^2	1.2×10^4 – 4.5×10^4	110	Clam, shrimp	[18]
	AuE	DPV	0.17	0.3 – 3×10^4	85	Mussel	[19]
	Au@PAN	DPV	0.3	0.3 – 3×10^4	3500	Shellfish	[20]
	PAMAM/SiO ₂ /dSi/Au	Capacitance-voltage	26.9	1.5×10^2 – 3×10^4	60	Mussel	[22]
	PAH/SiO ₂ /dSi/Au	Capacitance-voltage	3	30 – 3×10^4	60	Mussel	[23]
	AuE	DPV	3×10^2	3×10^2 – 3×10^5	30	Shellfish	[24]
	AuNPs/CE	SWV	1.6	5.4 – 6×10^4	20	Water	[26]
	STX-BSA/pLL/AuNPs/GSPE	DPV	7.9	0.01–8	85 + 250 s/channel	Mussel	This work

AgNPs: silver nanoparticles; AuE: gold electrode; AuNPs: gold nanoparticles; CE: carbon electrode; CS: chitosan; CV: cyclic voltammetry; DPV: differential pulse voltammetry; DR: detection range; dSi: doped silicon; GCE: glassy carbon electrode; LOD: limit of detection; OA-BSA: okadaic acid-bovine serum albumin conjugate; PAH: poly(allylamine hydrochloride); PAMAM: poly(amidoamine); PAN: polyacrylonitrile; pLL: poly(L-lysine); SPCE: screen-printed carbon electrode; STX-BSA: saxitoxin-bovine serum albumin conjugate; sw: silicon wafer; SWV: square wave voltammetry; THMS: triple-helix molecular switch.

and STX [33], respectively), were placed onto the realized sensor surface: in this way, the competition between bound and free OA or STX molecules, for the binding with their own aptamer, was allowed. An enzymatic conjugate between streptavidin and alkaline phosphatase was used to trace the competition reaction, by means of the biotin moieties of the aptamer sequences already bound to the BSA complexes. The enzymatic substrate 1-naphthyl phosphate was hydrolyzed by the enzyme and, finally, the electroactive product (1-naphthol) was detected by differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) measurements. A signal-off behavior, according to the competitive format used, was retrieved. Finally, the applicability of the developed strategy for seafood safety monitoring purposes was tested by the analysis of mussel samples spiked with OA or STX, and the obtained results were compared with those retrieved with a commercial enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kit. The novelty of the proposed aptamer-based sensors to detect phycotoxins is thus given by the combination of multiple elements, such as (i) the use of inexpensive graphite-based screen-printed cells, which eliminates the need for time-consuming cleaning and conditioning procedures of common solid electrodes, without mentioning the ease of device miniaturization provided by these transducers and (ii) a competitive detection format based on the use of BSA as a carrier protein, which promotes binding processes between the targets and the bioreceptors. Moreover, the use of a micro-sized potentiostat for the voltammetric detection could allow the interfacing with personal electronic devices (e.g., tablets, smartphones, etc.), making the applicability of the sensors even simpler and more effective, as they could also be used by non-experienced personnel.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

Tetrachloroauric acid (HAuCl_4), sulphuric acid 97 % (H_2SO_4), aniline ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}$), anthranilic acid ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NO}_2$), perchloric acid (HClO_4), L-lysine hydrochloride ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\cdot\text{HCl}$), N-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-N'-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\cdot\text{HCl}$, EDC), N-hydroxysuccinimide ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{NO}_3$, NHS), bovine serum albumin (BSA), okadaic acid (OA), saxitoxin (STX), brevetoxin-3 (PbTx-3), gonyautoxin-1 (GTX-1), gonyautoxin-4 (GTX-4), streptavidin-alkaline phosphatase enzyme conjugate (St-ALP), 1-naphthyl phosphate disodium salt (1-NPP), methanol (CH_4O), acetonitrile ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{N}$), acetic acid ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2$), tris (hydroxymethyl)aminomethane ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3$, TRIS), di-sodium hydrogen phosphate (Na_2HPO_4), sodium di-hydrogen phosphate dihydrate ($\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), diethanolamine ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2$, DEA), sodium chloride (NaCl), potassium chloride (KCl), magnesium chloride hexahydrate ($\text{MgCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), potassium ferrocyanide ($\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$), potassium ferricyanide ($\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$) were purchased from Merck (Milan, Italy). Okadaic acid-bovine serum albumin conjugate (OA-BSA) solution, saxitoxin-bovine serum albumin conjugate (STX-BSA) solution and the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits for OA and STX were purchased from Creative Diagnostics (Shirley, NY, USA).

All chemicals were of analytical grade, and all solutions were prepared in deionized water (resistivity: 18 M Ω) from a Milli-Q system.

The biotinylated DNA aptamer sequences (apt-BIO) used in this work were synthesized and purified by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) from Biomers.net GmbH (Ulm, Germany) and are reported in [Table S1](#).

The buffer solutions used in this work are the following.

- polymerization buffer: 50 mM phosphate buffer, pH 7.4;
- activation buffer: 0.1 M phosphate buffer, 0.1 M NaCl, pH 5.0;
- immobilization buffer: 0.1 M phosphate buffer, 0.1 M NaCl, pH 7.4;
- storage buffer: 20 mM TRIS, 15 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl_2 , pH 7.4;
- binding buffer: 0.5 M TRIS, 15 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl_2 , pH 7.4;
- detection buffer: 0.1 M DEA buffer, 0.1 M KCl, 1 mM MgCl_2 , pH 9.6.

2.2. Apparatus

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and chronoamperometry measurements were performed with a PalmSens2 portable potentiostat/galvanostat (PalmSens BV, Houten, The Netherlands) controlled by PStace 5.11 software for data acquisition and elaboration. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were performed with an Autolab PGSTAT 30(2) potentiostat/galvanostat (Eco Chemie BV, Utrecht, The Netherlands) controlled by NOVA 2.1.8 software for data acquisition and elaboration. Differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) measurements were performed using an ECSens micro-sized potentiostat (MicruX Technologies, Gijón, Spain) controlled by EC Manager Lite 1.1 software for data acquisition and elaboration. The assay was developed on C10 screen-printed electrochemical cells (ED-SIPE-C10), comprising a 3 mm-diameter graphite-based working electrode, a graphite counter electrode and a silver pseudo-reference electrode on a 250 μm polyethylene terephthalate substrate (MicruX Technologies, Gijón, Spain). All the reported potentials refer to the pseudo-reference silver screen-printed electrode, and all the measurements were carried out at room temperature.

2.3. Aptamers aliquots

Lyophilized DNA aptamers were reconstituted in storage buffer to a final concentration of 100 μM , then diluted in binding buffer to the desired concentration. Stock solutions were aliquoted and stored at -20°C until use to avoid repeated freeze-thaw cycles.

2.4. Phycotoxins standard solutions

Standard solutions of OA and STX were prepared daily by diluting the purchased stock solutions (20 $\mu\text{g/g}$, in methanol for OA, in hydrochloric acid for STX, in acetonitrile for PbTx-3 and in acetic acid for GTX-1/4, respectively) in binding buffer. The dilution ratios were chosen to make the final solutions contain the lowest percentage of the organic solvent and the acid as possible: this was done to avoid any interference arising from a possible dissolution of the insulating layer present on the screen-printed cells (SPCs), which can affect the results of the electrochemical measurements.

2.5. Development steps of an aptamer-based assay for parallel detection of okadaic acid and saxitoxin

The scheme of the realized aptasensors for OA or STX determination based on a competitive approach is shown in [Fig. 1](#).

The graphite-based screen-printed working electrodes were progressively modified by the electrodeposition of gold nanoparticles and then by the electropolymerization of aniline/anthranilic acid couple or L-lysine. The conjugate between bovine serum albumin and the toxin (OA or STX) was then immobilized by covalent binding between the carboxylic moieties of the polymers and the amino groups of the protein, exploiting EDC/NHS chemistry. The immobilization step was followed by a blocking step of the unreacted activated carboxylic groups by incubation with L-lysine: this step was necessary to further reduce non-specific adsorption phenomena, already partially obtained by the surface coverage provided by BSA. Solutions containing different concentrations of the toxin (OA or STX) and a fixed amount of the biotinylated aptamer (40mer-BIO or 34mer-BIO) were analyzed. The biotinylated complexes formed onto the aptasensor surface were labelled with the St-ALP conjugate: this enzyme catalyzes the hydrolysis of 1-NPP substrate to 1-naphthol (1-NPOH) electroactive product, which was finally detected by DPV.

2.5.1. Electrodeposition of gold nanoparticles

The surface of screen-printed C10 cells was primarily modified by the electrodeposition of gold nanoparticles using chronoamperometry

Fig. 1. Scheme of the developed aptamer assay for parallel okadaic acid (OA) and saxitoxin (STX) detection. **A)** Immobilization of a conjugate between bovine serum albumin and OA (OA-BSA) or STX (STX-BSA) onto poly(aniline-co-anthranilic acid)/gold nanoparticles- or poly(L-lysine)/gold nanoparticles-modified screen-printed C10 electrodes (p(ANI-co-AA)/AuNPs/C10 or pLL/AuNPs/C10), followed by the blocking of unreacted activated carboxylic groups with L-lysine; **B)** affinity reaction between OA/STX and the biotinylated aptamer (Apt-BIO) in solution, followed by a competition between free and immobilized OA or STX molecules; **C)** coupling with streptavidin-alkaline phosphatase enzyme conjugate (St-ALP); **D)** incubation with 1-naphthyl phosphate (1-NPP) enzymatic substrate and electrochemical detection of 1-naphthol (1-NPOH) by differential pulse voltammetry (DPV).

technique. A 2 mM solution of HAuCl_4 in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 was dropped on the C10 cells and the electrodeposition was conducted by applying a fixed potential of -0.2 V for 130 s, as previously reported [34]. The AuNPs-modified C10 cells (AuNPs/C10) were then washed with Milli-Q water to remove residual precursors and free ions from the surface.

2.5.2. Electrodeposition of poly(aniline-co-anthranilic acid) copolymer

At first, AuNPs/C10 cells were further modified by electro-polymerizing a mixture of aniline and anthranilic acid to form a copolymer (p(ANI-co-AA)) by means of CV. A 2.5 mM equimolar solution of aniline and anthranilic acid in 50 mM HClO_4 was dropped onto the AuNPs-modified cells, and the potential was cycled from -200 mV to $+1000$ mV for 10 cycles at 50 mV/s. The modified electrodes were washed with Milli-Q water to remove excess monomer from the surface and then stored at 4 °C in dry conditions.

2.5.3. Electrodeposition of poly(L-lysine)

Following an alternative procedure, AuNPs/C10 cells were modified by the electrodeposition of layer of poly(L-lysine) (pLL). L-lysine polymerization was performed by CV by dropping a 20 mM L-Lys solution in polymerization buffer onto the electrodic surface and by scanning the potential between -500 mV and $+1500$ mV at 100 mV/s for 20 cycles. The modified electrodes were washed with Milli-Q water to remove excess monomer from the surface and then stored at 4 °C in dry conditions.

2.5.4. Immobilization of the phycotoxins-bovine serum albumin conjugates

The nanocomposites polymeric platforms were used to covalently immobilize the bovine serum albumin conjugates with OA or STX. To increase the reactivity of the carboxylic groups of the two polymers, an activation step was performed by dropping a mixture of 0.2 M NHS and 0.4 M EDC in activation buffer onto the nanostructured working electrodes and incubating it for 30 min at 4 °C. After this time, the electrodes were washed with immobilization buffer. The OA-BSA or STX-BSA conjugate was diluted at 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in immobilization buffer from the purchased stock solutions (10.1 mg/mL for OA-BSA and 0.5 mg/mL for STX-BSA, respectively) and dropped onto the activated working electrodes. Then, the cells were incubated overnight (≈ 16 h) in sealed Petri dishes in a humid atmosphere to avoid evaporation processes. The modified electrodes were washed with immobilization buffer to remove unbound macromolecules. A further step was performed by dropping a 0.1 mg/mL L-Lys solution in immobilization buffer onto the modified working electrodes for 30 min to block the unreacted activated carboxylic sites. A further washing step in immobilization buffer was performed; then, the modified C10 cells were stored at 4 °C for further use.

2.5.5. Electrochemical characterization of the building steps of the platform

An electrochemical characterization of the developed sensing platforms was performed by both CV and EIS techniques in presence of a 5 mM solution of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{-4/-3}$ redox probe (equimolar mixture in 0.1 M KCl). Regarding the voltammetric measurements, the potential was

scanned from -500 mV to $+800$ mV at 50 mV/s scan rate. A further characterization was done by performing CV measurements in the same experimental conditions, but at different scan rates ($25, 50, 75, 100$ mV/s). The height of both anodic and cathodic peaks (i_p , in [A]) was taken as the electrochemical signal and plotted against the square root of the scan rate ($v^{1/2}$, in [V/s]). The obtained curves were fitted with the Randles-Sevcik equation [35]:

$$i_p = (2.69 \cdot 10^5) n^{3/2} A c (D v)^{1/2}, \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of electrons transferred in the redox event, A (in [cm²]) is the electroactive surface area, c (in [mol/cm³]) is bulk concentration of the selected redox probe and D (in [cm²/s]) its diffusion coefficient. Regarding the impedimetric measurements, a voltage of 10 mV in amplitude (peak-to-peak), within the frequency range from 100 kHz to 1 Hz, was superimposed on the applied bias potential. The DC potential was set up to $+130$ mV, the formal potential of the ferro/ferricyanide redox couple. After each CV or EIS measurement, the SPCs were discarded.

2.5.6. Okadaic acid and saxitoxin competitive detection

OA and STX parallel detections were performed by dropping solutions containing a proper concentration of biotinylated DNA aptamer (apt-BIO) and different concentrations of the analytes in binding buffer onto the sensor surfaces to allow the competitive reaction to occur. Specifically, the competition for the binding with the aptamer was performed in two steps. In the first step, the affinity reaction between free phycotoxin (in the concentration range 0 – 80 ng/mL for OA and 0 – 8 ng/mL for STX) and 20 nM apt-BIO is allowed to proceed in microcentrifuge tubes for 15 min; in the second step, these mixtures were dropped onto the modified working electrodes to allow free aptamer molecules to interact with the phycotoxins immobilized on the surface in the form of BSA conjugates. After 30 min, the sensors were rinsed with detection buffer to remove eventually unbound molecules.

2.5.7. Enzymatic labelling and electrochemical measurements

The biotinylated complexes formed on the sensor surface were labelled with a solution containing 1 U/mL of the St-ALP conjugate and 8 mg/mL of BSA in detection buffer for 20 min, and then thoroughly rinsed with detection buffer. Finally, each SPC was incubated with a 1 mg/mL 1-NPP in detection buffer. After 20 min, the electroactive enzymatic product, 1-NPOH, was detected via DPV (potential range: 0 – $+600$ mV; step potential: 5 mV; modulation amplitude: 70 mV; modulation time: 0.05 s; interval time: 1.25 s; scan rate: 4 mV/s). The current peak height was taken as the electrochemical signal. The signal is expressed in relative percentage units as S_x/S_0 (i.e., the ratio between the signal obtained in presence of the analyte with respect to that of the blank) and plotted against OA or STX concentration. The obtained curve showed the typical sigmoidal shape of a competitive assay and was fitted by using OriginPro 2024 software (OriginLab) with a logistic sigmoidal equation:

$$y = y_2 + \frac{y_1 - y_2}{1 + \left(\frac{x}{x_0}\right)^p} \quad (2)$$

where y_1 and y_2 are the ordinate values at the top and at the bottom plateau of the curve, respectively; x_0 is the center of the curve; p is the power coefficient.

2.6. Interference study

To test the selectivity of the developed biosensors, control experiments were performed in presence of potentially interfering phycotoxins such as brevetoxin-3 (PbTx-3), gonyautoxin-1 (GTX-1) and gonyautoxin-4 (GTX-4), including OA and STX themselves. The signals obtained in presence of the interfering compounds were compared with those

obtained for OA or STX alone. To test the selectivity of the OA biosensor, each toxin (i.e., PbTx-3, GTX-1, GTX-4 and STX) was tested at 5 ng/mL, while for STX biosensor, each toxin (i.e., PbTx-3, GTX-1, GTX-4 and OA) was tested at 3 ng/mL. In addition, a solution containing 0 ng/mL of the toxins and 20 nM of apt-BIO sequence was tested as the blank solution.

2.7. Real samples analysis

In order to demonstrate the applicability of the developed strategy, mussel samples were analyzed with the modified C10 cells. Mussels were purchased in a local supermarket: then, the first step was the pretreatment of mussels in order to properly extract OA and STX from this complex matrix and make them available for the detection with the developed sensors. As reported in ELISA kits, mussels were thoroughly rinsed with deionized water, then wiped and homogenized with a blender. A 1 g portion of the homogenized mussels was then vortexed with 6 mL of a hydroalcoholic solution of methanol (80% v/v). The mixture was centrifuged for 10 min at 3000 rpm/g; then, the supernatant was collected, and the remaining mussel tissue residue was once more suspended in 2 mL of the aforementioned solution. The mixture was centrifuged for 10 min and the supernatant was added to that previously obtained. The final volume of collected supernatant was brought to 10 mL with the hydroalcoholic solution and then filtered with a 0.45 μ m filter. The final extracts were appropriately diluted in binding buffer and the response was determined by DPV measurements, under the same conditions used for OA and STX calibration curves.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Modification and characterization of the C10 SPCs

The presented aptasensors were built on a nanocomposite platform made of AuNPs and a conductive polymeric layer of p(ANI-co-AA) or pLL with a double aim: to improve the electrochemical performance of C10 SPCs and to provide a scaffold for the immobilization of the conjugates between the phycotoxins (OA or STX) and BSA. Polyaniline (pANI) has become utterly popular as a conductive polymer to develop sensors and biosensors, both in combination with metal nanoparticles, such as gold ones [36,37], or conjugated carboxylic acids, such as anthranilic acid [38]: in fact, as extensively reported in the literature, pANI owns the ability to become easily doped or de-doped by means of acid/base processes, which may improve significantly its conductivity but, at the same time, may also represent an important issue when dealing with biosensing applications [39–41]. With the aim of maximizing this improvement, we have decided to test both these doping ways at the same time, by electropolymerizing a mixture of aniline and anthranilic acid on a gold nanoparticles-modified working electrode printed with a graphite-based ink. Moreover, it has been demonstrated that aniline tends to adsorb on polycrystalline gold electrodes from both acidic and neutral electrolyte solutions [42], which could probably support aniline electropolymerization in an easier and oriented way. However, despite the good performances of “classic” conducting polymers, a critical point when dealing with them is still present, and regards the carcinogenicity related to the monomers they are constituted, primarily aniline. Therefore, nontoxic, biocompatible and biodegradable alternatives are required, also to ensure safe work conditions for operators during the modification of the SPCs. In this regard, amino acids-based polymers have recently drawn a lot of attention due to their advantages, including non-toxicity, biodegradability, biocompatibility, and a wide number of side functional groups [43].

Among them, poly(L-lysine) (pLL) has great potential as an electrode-modifying agent due to its good stability and reproducibility and has been employed in the development of electrochemical sensors and biosensors [44]. Moreover, at physiological pH, L-lysine units in pLL may bear positively charged hydrophilic amino groups, which could work as an immobilization platform for enzymes [45,46] or, generally speaking,

negatively charged proteins, such as BSA. Pushed by the above reasons, we have decided to go further in the study by substituting the copolymer with pLL, thus testing an additional platform to detect OA and STX.

At first, a preliminary CV characterization was performed on the nanomaterials-modified C10 electrodes in presence of 5 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{-4/-3} (equimolar solution in 0.1 M KCl) reversible redox probe at different scan rates. The electroactive surface area (A) was then calculated for each platform using the Randles-Sevcik equation (1): the obtained values are reported in Table 2.

The presence of gold nanoparticles causes a dramatic increase in the electroactive area values, due to both the enhanced conductivity of the metal and the nanostructuring of the graphite-based C10 surface. These values decrease after the electrodeposition of p(ANI-co-AA) or pLL, as the presence of a polymeric layer could provide a smoothing effect on the gold-modified surface: however, the presence of pLL causes a slightly smaller decrease respect to the copolymer, probably due to the positive charge of the poly(amino acid) at neutral pH values.

Then, to gain insights into the processes occurring at the electroodic surface, the building steps of the two nanocomposite sensing platforms, including the immobilization of the phycotoxin-BSA conjugates, were characterized using CV and EIS in presence of 5 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{-4/-3} (equimolar solution in 0.1 M KCl) reversible redox couple, both in the case of p(ANI-co-AA) (Fig. S1) and in that of pLL (Fig. S2).

The electrochemical quantities derived from the cyclovoltammograms are listed in Table 3.

CV and EIS measurements gave complementary results for both platforms: in fact, the current peak height (*i_p*) and the charge-transfer resistance (*R_{ct}*) show opposite trends in each case. Gold nanoparticles enhance the conductivity and reversibility features of C10 cells (*i.e.*, increase in *i_p* and decrease in ΔE_p values), which are partially attenuated with the subsequent electropolymerization (*i.e.*, decrease in *i_p* values and increase in ΔE_p). When pLL is present, a slightly higher value of *i_p* is retrieved, probably because of the positive charge of the polymer at physiological pH. These findings are also consistent with the above-observed trend retrieved for the electroactive surface areas. The immobilization of phycotoxin-BSA conjugates causes a dramatic increase in *R_{ct}* values when the copolymer is present, as the conjugates may hinder the accessibility of the electrode and, thus, the exchange of electrons with the redox probe. On the other hand, a different behavior was observed in the case of pLL, as *R_{ct}* values remained quite similar after the immobilization process, probably because of a smaller amount of conjugates being immobilized on this polymer, due to a lower number of carboxylic groups available for immobilization compared to the copolymer.

From the reported results, it can be asserted that the modification of C10 cells with the polymer/gold nanocomposites enhanced the reversibility of the redox reaction, as a decrease in the ΔE_p values was observed and the $|i_{p,a}/i_{p,c}|$ ratio approached the unity in almost all cases. This behavior is particularly prominent when pLL is present, with lower ΔE_p and higher *i_p* values with respect to the copolymer.

3.2. OA/STX competitive assay

As previously reported by our research group [30], a competitive assay based on the immobilization of a BSA conjugate was demonstrated to successfully determine the presence of aflatoxin B₁ in maize samples.

Table 2
Electroactive area values of the nanomaterials-modified C10 electrodes.

	A _a (mm ²)	A _c (mm ²)	A _{av} (mm ²)	SD (mm ²)
C10	7.7	6.6	7.2	0.8
AuNPs/C10	12.4	11.4	11.9	0.7
p(ANI-co-AA)/AuNPs/C10	6.8	6.6	6.7	0.1
pLL/AuNPs/C10	8.8	8.4	8.6	0.3

A_a: anodic area; A_c: cathodic area; A_{av}: average area; SD: standard deviation.

Table 3

List of peak potentials (*E_p*) and current peak heights (*i_p*) for each building step of the two platforms.

	<i>E_{p,a}</i> (V)	<i>E_{p,c}</i> (V)	ΔE_p (V)	<i>i_{p,a}</i> (μA)	<i>i_{p,c}</i> (μA)	$ i_{p,a}/i_{p,c} $
C10	0.320	-0.010	0.330	63.823	-54.818	1.2
AuNPs/C10	0.195	0.070	0.125	102.342	-94.023	1.1
p(ANI-co-AA)/AuNPs/C10	0.310	-0.065	0.375	56.391	-54.970	1.0
OA-BSA/p(ANI-co-AA)/AuNPs/C10	0.305	-0.005	0.310	55.874	-51.297	1.1
STX-BSA/p(ANI-co-AA)/AuNPs/C10	0.290	0.020	0.270	41.403	-40.753	1.0
pLL/AuNPs/C10	0.285	0.000	0.285	73.059	-69.701	1.0
OA-BSA/pLL/AuNPs/C10	0.255	0.065	0.190	86.733	-83.086	1.0
STX-BSA/pLL/AuNPs/C10	0.260	0.070	0.190	84.762	-80.923	1.0

Thus, we wanted to verify the feasibility of such assay even in marine toxins detection, as the use of carrier proteins like BSA has proven to be effective in competitive processes involving molecules with a low molecular weight (<1 kDa). Moreover, this double interaction-based strategy could enhance the binding efficiency: as initially the molecular recognition of the analytes occurs in solution, rather than on the surface, the steric hindrance is drastically reduced, which is a crucial point in the analysis of small molecules like phycotoxins. The use of this format reduces the need to control the receptor density and its spatial organization, which are critical parameters, instead, when aptamers are immobilized on electroodic surfaces [47].

To find the best conditions for the competitive assay to work in this new application, key experimental parameters, such as apt-BIO concentration, affinity reaction time (*i.e.*, that foreseeing the interaction between apt-BIO and OA or STX in microtubes) and competition time (*i.e.*, that foreseeing the interaction between apt-BIO and OA-BSA or STX-BSA onto the sensor surface) were carefully re-optimized. Experiments for the optimization of the apt-BIO concentration were performed by incubating the biosensors with 0 ng/mL (*S*₀) and 5 ng/mL OA (*S*₅) or 1 ng/mL STX (*S*₁) solutions containing different apt-BIO concentrations. The signal variation ((*S*₅-*S*₀)/*S*₀) for OA and ((*S*₁-*S*₀)/*S*₀) for STX is reported in Fig. 2 in percentage units.

In a competitive assay format, the addition of the analyte is intended to cause a decrease of the current peak height with respect to the blank, due to the decrease in the availability of the labelled aptamer for the binding with the immobilized phycotoxins (*i.e.*, OA-BSA and STX-BSA conjugates). However, this behavior was not always observed, both for OA and STX, when apt-BIO concentration is above 20 nM. This could be probably due to residual non-specific adsorption phenomena at high concentrations of the selected oligonucleotides in presence of such low amounts of phycotoxins. In fact, a decrease in the signal with respect to the blank solution (that is, a negative value of the aforementioned ratios) was observed only in presence of 10 nM or 20 nM of the apt-BIO sequences (40mer-BIO for OA and 34mer-BIO for STX). Specifically, among these two concentration values, 20 nM was chosen for all the subsequent experiments as it provided the highest reduction of the signal (*i.e.*, the longest bars in the negative quadrants of Fig. 2).

The optimization of apt-BIO incubation times was conducted in a similar way by incubating the modified C10 with 5 ng/mL OA or 1 ng/mL STX and 20 nM of 40mer-BIO or 34mer-BIO, respectively. Different incubation times for apt-BIO, both in microtubes and on the sensors' surface, were tested, in order to find the combination of these times that provides the best performance of the sensors in terms of signal decrease and reproducibility for both targets. The results obtained in these experimental conditions are reported in Table 4.

Fig. 2. Aptamers' concentration optimization. The signal is reported as $(S_{5/1}-S_0)/S_0$ percentage units, that is the signal variation with respect to the blank obtained in presence of **a)** 5 ng/mL of okadaic acid (OA) or **b)** 1 ng/mL of saxitoxin (STX). Each measurement was repeated at least three times using different biosensors.

Table 4

Optimization of the assay times. The signal is reported as $S_{5/1}/S_0$ (%), that is the relative signal obtained with 5 ng/mL for OA and 1 ng/mL for STX with respect to the blank. Each concentration was repeated at least three times using different electrodes.

Affinity reaction time (min)	Competition time (min)	Okadaic acid		Saxitoxin	
		S_5/S_0 (%)	% RSD	S_1/S_0 (%)	% RSD
15	10	91	11	79	6
15	20	93	5	68	22
15	30	62	1	67	2
15	45	84	1	88	1
15	60	86	9	83	8
5	30	61	6	73	5
10	30	55	1	45	4
15	30	31	1	37	1
30	30	34	3	59	16
45	30	44	7	57	4

RSD: relative standard deviation.

The best results for both sensors were retrieved when an incubation time of 15 min in microtubes and an incubation of 30 min onto the sensor surface were used, as the relative signal S_x/S_0 (*i.e.*, the signal obtained in presence of the analyte with respect to that of the blank), reported in percent units, reaches the lowest value.

Fig. 3. Calibration curves for **a)** okadaic acid (OA) and **b)** saxitoxin (STX) on pLL/AuNPs/C10 platform. Each experimental point corresponds to $\%S_x/S_0 \pm SD$. Each measurement was repeated at least three times using different biosensors.

3.3. OA/STX detection

Under the previously optimized experimental conditions, calibration curves for OA and STX were obtained in buffered solutions by the developed indirect competitive format. Different solutions at increasing OA or STX concentration, containing a fixed amount of 20 nM apt-BIO, were analyzed. The relative signal showed a decreasing trend, as expected from a competitive assay (Fig. S3).

The calibration curves show correlation coefficients (R^2) of 0.988 for OA and 0.9985 for STX. The limit of detection (LOD) for each assay was calculated by the evaluation of the average response of the blank minus three times its standard deviation and resulted to be 74.7 pg/mL for OA and 8.5 pg/mL for STX. Then, as already sketched in the previous section (*i.e.*, 3.2), OA and STX detection in standard solutions was again performed, in the same experimental conditions as already described, on the platform containing pLL, and the results were compared with those obtained with the platform containing the copolymer (Fig. 3).

The calibration curves obtained in this new experimental setup show correlation coefficients (R^2) of 0.9992 for OA and 0.9975 for STX, confirming that the nature of the polymer does not affect the efficiency of the assay itself. The LOD for each assay was calculated as previously explained and resulted to be 66.4 pg/mL for OA and 7.9 pg/mL for STX. A comparable behavior of the dose-response curves for OA and STX between the two platforms was retrieved, thus demonstrating the suitability of poly(L-lysine) in replacing the copolymer: for all the

aforementioned reasons, pLL was used in each one of the subsequent experiments, taking also into account the advantages that a non-toxic platform can provide, as the easy manageability with almost no risks for the end-users. Moreover, from a purely practical point of view, solutions of L-Lys can be more easily prepared and stored respect to aniline-anthranilic acid ones, which foresee mixing two different species and the storage in cold and dark conditions.

The shelf life of the developed sensors was studied by storing a batch of OA/STX-BSA-modified pLL/AuNPs/C10 in dry conditions at 4 °C. The stability of the developed biosensors was assessed by assaying them in presence of a fixed amount of the analytes at regular time intervals up to two weeks. The S_x/S_0 value and the average %RSD were calculated over 15 modified SPCs. The results showed that the signal (i.e., the ratio of the current peak height in presence of the toxin with respect to that obtained for the blank) increases with passing time, thus meaning a sub-estimation of the amount of the toxin – about 50 % of the initial amount per week. However, the retrieved reproducibility was acceptable, making the sensors a reliable device to be applied in food analysis.

3.4. Interference study

The selectivity of the developed biosensors was determined in presence of potentially interfering marine toxins, such as PbTx-3, GTX-1 and GTX-4, both individually and grouped together. In this study, OA and STX themselves were considered as potential interferents one for another. Each toxin was tested at 5 ng/mL in the case of OA and at 3 ng/mL in the case of STX (Fig. 4).

Good results were retrieved in all the tested combinations, showing that the biosensors are characterized by good selectivity. In fact, the interferent toxins cause a change in the S_x/S_0 signal of few percentage points, with the most notable variation retrieved in the case of the analogous toxins (PbTx-3 for OA and GTX-1/4 for STX), due to their structural similarity to the target molecules; on the other hand, the phycotoxin for which each biosensor is dedicated causes a variation of about 50 %, regardless the presence or absence of the interferents.

3.5. Analysis of mussel samples

As the final application of the developed sensors is to detect marine toxins, such as OA and STX, in mussels, key experimental parameters were studied and optimized to achieve the best performance possible. First, to assess the evaluation of the matrix effect and to select the most proper dilution factor for real samples analysis, commercially available mussels were pretreated. Solutions containing a fixed amount of the toxins (1 ng/mL of OA or 0.5 ng/mL of STX) were prepared in mussel

extracts at different dilution factors and analyzed in the same experimental conditions of those used for the calibration curves (Fig. S4).

From the reported results when the toxins were added after the extraction procedure, the correlation between the dilution factor and the obtained biosensor response could unfortunately not be seen. The experiment was then repeated by adding the toxins before the extraction procedure (Fig. S5).

As it can be observed, when the toxins were added before the extraction procedure, a correlation between the dilution factor and the biosensor response was obtained: the dilution factor 1:25 was chosen as the most appropriate as the percent signal difference was the highest to be retrieved. OA and STX were then detected in mussel complex matrix under the same experimental conditions as previously described, and the results were compared with those retrieved in standard solutions (Fig. 5).

The sigmoidal behavior of the calibration curve related to a competitive format can be observed even performing the assay in mussel extract, even if the maximum decrease of the signal is around 70 % for OA and 50 % for STX, while in standard solutions these values were around 80 % for OA and 75 % for STX, respectively. This discrepancy could be addressed to the complexity of the analyzed matrix, which can affect the efficiency of the assay, especially at high concentrations of the analytes, without compromising its ability of detecting the two phycotoxins. Based on the comparison of the calibration curves in standard solutions and in mussel extract, recovery values were calculated for OA and STX and compared with those retrieved from the commercial ELISA kits (Table 5).

Regarding OA detection, higher recovery values were retrieved for the aptasensors compared to ELISAs, while this trend is inverted in the case of STX. However, in almost all cases, an acceptable bias was found for spiked mussel samples, assessing the applicability of the aptasensors in real samples. The selectivity of the developed sensors was also assessed in mussel extract as previously described (Fig. 6).

The results were comparable with those obtained in standard solutions, as almost no interference of STX for OA was found, and *vice versa*, while the most notable variation was retrieved in the case of the analogous phycotoxins.

4. Conclusions

This work developed two electrochemical aptamer sensors, both based on a competitive format, for parallel detection of the phycotoxins okadaic acid (OA) and saxitoxin (STX). Mass-produced, screen-printed graphite electrodes were modified with gold nanoparticles and a conductive polymer – either the copolymer of aniline and anthranilic

Fig. 4. Selectivity of the developed sensors built on pLL-based platform for a) okadaic acid (OA) (5 ng/mL each) and b) saxitoxin (STX) (3 ng/mL each) in standard solutions. Each measurement was repeated at least three times using different biosensors.

Fig. 5. Comparison of calibration curves obtained in standard solutions (● and ●) and in mussel extract (● and ●) for a) okadaic acid (OA) and b) saxitoxin (STX) on pLL/AuNPs/C10 platform. Each experimental point corresponds to $\%S_x/S_0 \pm SD$. Each measurement was repeated at least three times using different biosensors.

Table 5

Analysis of okadaic acid (OA) or saxitoxin (STX) spiked mussel extract.

	OA		STX	
	Aptasensor	ELISA kit	Aptasensor	ELISA kit
Toxin spiked (ng/mL)				
1.0	1.0	0.20	0.05	0.0125
2.5	2.5	0.50	0.10	0.0250
5.0	5.0	1.00	0.50	0.200
Toxin found (ng/mL)				
0.7	0.7	0.22	0.07	0.0109
2.2	2.2	0.31	0.13	0.0235
4.8	4.8	0.29	0.44	0.194
Recovery (%)				
74	74	110	135	87
89	89	62	131	94
95	95	29	88	97
%RSD				
8	8	3	7	5
5	5	7	10	6
3	3	5	4	4

RSD: relative standard deviation.

acid or poly(L-lysine). These two nanostructured platforms were electrochemically characterized and then used in the development steps of the same assay format to detect both OA and STX: however, to further enhance the performance of the sensors, even in terms of user-friendliness, poly(L-lysine) was chosen to replace the copolymer, as the related monomer is not as carcinogenic as aniline. After a careful optimization of all the steps of the assay, the parallel detection of the two

phycotoxins was achieved in less than 90 min: dose-response curves were obtained in the range 0.1–80 ng/mL for OA and 0.01–8 ng/mL for STX, with detection limits of 66.4 pg/mL and 7.9 pg/mL, respectively. Finally, the developed sensors were successfully applied in the analysis of a real complex matrix as mussel extracts and compared with commercial ELISA kits, retrieving acceptable recovery values. The pre-treatment of mussel samples is a fundamental step in the analysis: as it foresees the homogenization of tissues and the extraction of the phycotoxins with organic solvent, it does not currently allow *in vivo* monitoring of phycotoxins and still could constitute an issue even for real-time monitoring purposes, due to the multiple steps needed to complete the whole process. However, further improvement of the extraction procedure and/or the sensitivity of the detection may lead to a future application of the sensors even on living organisms, thus extending their usefulness to phycotoxins monitoring in different scenarios (e.g., aquacultures, points of sale, etc.).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Anna Szymczyk-Drozd: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Giulia Selvolini:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mattia Carbone:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Giovanna Marrazza:** Writing –

Fig. 6. Selectivity of the developed sensors for both a) okadaic acid (OA) (5 ng/mL each) and b) saxitoxin (STX) (3 ng/mL each) in mussel extract. Each measurement was repeated at least three times using different biosensors.

review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2025.129136>.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- D.M. Anderson, A.D. Cembella, G.M. Hallegraef, Progress in understanding harmful algal blooms: paradigm shifts and new technologies for research, monitoring, and management, *Ann. Rev. Mar. Sci.* 4 (2012) 143–176, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-120308-081121>.
- E. Berdalet, L.E. Fleming, R. Gowen, K. Davidson, P. Hess, L.C. Backer, S.K. Moore, P. Hoagland, H. Enevoldsen, Marine harmful algal blooms, human health and wellbeing: challenges and opportunities in the 21st century, *J. Mar. Biol. Assoc. United Kingdom* 96 (2016) 61–91, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025315415001733>.
- N. Young, R.A. Sharpe, R. Barciela, G. Nichols, K. Davidson, E. Berdalet, L. E. Fleming, Marine harmful algal blooms and human health: a systematic scoping review, *Harmful Algae* 98 (2020) 101901, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2020.101901>.
- H. Fujiki, E. Sueoka, T. Watanabe, M. Suganuma, The concept of the Okadaic acid class of tumor promoters is revived in endogenous protein inhibitors of protein phosphatase 2A, SET and CIP2A, in human cancers, *J. Cancer Res. Clin. Oncol.* 144 (2018) 2339–2349, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00432-018-2765-7>.
- K. Cusick, G. Saylor, An overview on the marine neurotoxin, saxitoxin: genetics, molecular targets, methods of detection and ecological functions, *Mar. Drugs* 11 (2013) 991–1018, <https://doi.org/10.3390/md11040991>.
- Marine biotoxins in shellfish - okadaic acid and analogues - scientific opinion of the panel on contaminants in the food chain, *EFSA J.* 6 (2008) 589, <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2008.589>.
- S.C. Finch, N.G. Webb, M.J. Boundy, D.T. Harwood, J.S. Munday, J.M. Sprosen, C. Somchit, R.B. Broadhurst, A sub-acute dosing study of saxitoxin and tetrodotoxin mixtures in mice suggests that the current paralytic shellfish toxin regulatory limit is fit for purpose, *Toxins* 15 (2023) 437, <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins15070437>.
- S. Ramalingam, R. Chand, C.B. Singh, A. Singh, Phosphorene-gold nanocomposite based microfluidic aptasensor for the detection of Okadaic acid, *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 135 (2019) 14–21, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2019.03.056>.
- V. Vogiazis, A. de la Cruz, S. Mishra, V. Shanov, W.R. Heineman, D.D. Dionysiou, A comprehensive review: development of electrochemical biosensors for detection of cyanotoxins in freshwater, *ACS Sens.* 4 (2019) 1151–1173, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssensors.9b00376>.
- L. Yang, H. Guo, Q. Gao, T. Hou, J. Zhang, X. Liu, F. Li, Integrating reliable Pt-S bond-mediated 3D DNA nanomachine with magnetic separation in a homogeneous electrochemical strategy for exosomal MicroRNA detection with low background and high sensitivity, *Anal. Chem.* 95 (2023) 17834–17842, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.3c03914>.
- J. Wu, B. He, Y. Wang, R. Zhao, Y. Zhang, C. Bai, M. Wei, H. Jin, W. Ren, Z. Suo, Y. Xu, ZIF-8 labelled a new electrochemical aptasensor based on PEI-PrGO/AuNWs for DON detection, *Talanta* 267 (2024) 125257, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2023.125257>.
- H. Khosropour, M. Keramat, W. Laiwattanapaisal, A dual action electrochemical molecularly imprinted aptasensor for ultra-trace detection of carbendazim, *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 243 (2024) 115754, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2023.115754>.
- T. Chen, T. Guo, J. Zhang, X. Liu, J. Chen, P. Wang, Y. Zhang, L. Ma, An electrochemical aptasensor based on ACEK enrichment for detection of AFB1, *Sensors Actuators B Chem.* 417 (2024) 136055, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.SNB.2024.136055>.
- H. Khosropour, M. Keramat, V. Primpray, C. Karuwan, F. Tasca, W. Laiwattanapaisal, An electrochemical aptamer-based biosensor for rapid and ultrasensitive detection of carbaryl by red blood cell-like MOFs, *Alexandria Eng. J.* 124 (2025) 1–11, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AEJ.2025.03.058>.
- Y. Liu, H. Lai, P. Ming, P. Chen, Q. Zhou, D. Sun, H. Zhai, Ultrasensitive ratiometric electrochemical aptasensor based on novel MnCo@C as nonenzyme catalysis for the detection of patulin, *Sensors Actuators B Chem.* 401 (2024) 135077, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SNB.2023.135077>.
- L. Yang, H. Guo, T. Hou, J. Zhang, F. Li, Metal-mediated Fe3O4@polydopamine-aptamer capture nanoprobe coupling multifunctional MXene@Au@Pt nanzyme for direct and portable photothermal analysis of circulating breast cancer cells, *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 234 (2023) 115346, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2023.115346>.
- Y. Chen, Y. Liu, P. Zhu, S. Liu, M. Wang, Y. Liu, Z. Wang, W. Chen, Z. Qu, L. Du, C. Wu, A 2D carbon nitride-based electrochemical aptasensor with reverse amplification for highly sensitive detection of okadaic acid in shellfish, *Anal. Methods* 16 (2024) 1538–1545, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3AY02002A>.
- W. Zeng, X. Tang, T. Wu, B. Han, L. Wu, Development of a highly sensitive aptamer-based electrochemical sensor for detecting saxitoxin based on K3Fe(CN)6 regulated silver nanoparticles, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1287 (2024) 342134, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2023.342134>.
- Y. Liu, S. Feng, R. Zhong, Y. Peng, G. Mu, J. Bai, W. Chen, Z. Qu, DNA walker coupled with nicking endonuclease for sensitive electrochemical detection of saxitoxin, *Sensors & Diagnostics* 3 (2024) 1353–1357, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4SD00167B>.
- J. Li, W. Zheng, Y. Gao, X. Liu, Z. Li, L. Zhang, Nanopillar array-based electrochemical aptamer sensor for STX sensitivity detection, *Anal. Methods* 16 (2024) 5433–5440, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4AY00932K>.
- Y. Tian, S. Liu, Y. Liu, Y. Chen, B. Noureen, L. Du, D. Jing, C. Wu, Triple-helix molecular switch-based light-addressable potentiometric aptasensor for the multi-channel highly sensitive label-free detection and spatiotemporal imaging of okadaic acid, *Sensors Actuators B Chem.* 389 (2023) 133892, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2023.133892>.
- N. Ullah, B. Noureen, Y. Tian, L. Du, W. Chen, C. Wu, Label-free detection of saxitoxin with field-effect device-based biosensor, *Nanomaterials* 12 (2022) 1505, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12091505>.
- B. Noureen, N. Ullah, Y. Tian, L. Du, W. Chen, C. Wu, P. Wang, An electrochemical PAH-Modified aptasensor for the label-free and highly-sensitive detection of saxitoxin, *Talanta* 240 (2022) 123185, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2021.123185>.
- W. Zheng, X. Liu, Q. Li, Z. Shu, Z. Li, L. Zhang, A simple electrochemical aptasensor for saxitoxin detection, *RSC Adv.* 12 (2022) 23801–23807, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2RA03690H>.
- N. Zeng, X. Wang, Y. Dong, Y. Yang, Y. Yin, L. Zhao, X. Wang, Aptasensor based on screen-printed carbon electrodes modified with CS/AuNPs for sensitive detection of Okadaic acid in shellfish, *J. Anal. Test.* 7 (2023) 128–135, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41664-022-00245-9>.
- A. Rhouati, M. Zourob, Development of a multiplexed electrochemical aptasensor for the detection of cyanotoxins, *Biosensors* 14 (2024) 268, <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios14060268>.
- Y. Qin, J. Li, J. Kuang, S. Shen, J. Jiang, Z. Zhang, C. Zhao, X. Zhou, B. Huang, B. Han, Sensitive time-resolved fluoroimmunoassay for the quantitative detection of Okadaic acid, *Front. Mar. Sci.* 9 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.961751>.
- F. Micheli, S. Di Stefano, D. Moscone, G. Pallechi, S. Marini, M. Coletta, R. Draisci, F. delli Quadri, Production of antibodies and development of highly sensitive formats of enzyme immunoassay for saxitoxin analysis, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 373 (2002) 678–684, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-002-1399-3>.
- A.M. Onaş, C. Dascălu, M.D. Raicopol, L. Pilan, Critical design factors for electrochemical aptasensors based on target-induced conformational changes: the case of small-molecule targets, *Biosens* 12 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/BIOS12100816>, 816 12 (2022) 816.
- G. Selvolini, M. Lettieri, L. Tassoni, S. Gastaldello, M. Grillo, C. Maran, G. Marrazza, Electrochemical enzyme-linked oligonucleotide array for aflatoxin B1 detection, *Talanta* 203 (2019) 49–57, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2019.05.044>.
- H. Gu, N. Duan, S. Wu, L. Hao, Y. Xia, X. Ma, Z. Wang, Graphene oxide-assisted non-immobilized SELEX of okadaic acid aptamer and the analytical application of aptasensor, *Sci. Rep.* 6 (2016) 1–9, <https://doi.org/10.1038/SREP21665>.
- H. Gu, L. Hao, N. Duan, S. Wu, Y. Xia, X. Ma, Z. Wang, A competitive fluorescent aptasensor for okadaic acid detection assisted by rolling circle amplification, *Microchim. Acta* 184 (2017) 2893–2899, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-017-2293-1>.
- X. Zheng, B. Hu, S.X. Gao, D.J. Liu, M.J. Sun, B.H. Jiao, L.H. Wang, A saxitoxin-binding aptamer with higher affinity and inhibitory activity optimized by rational site-directed mutagenesis and truncation, *Toxicon* 101 (2015) 41–47, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxicon.2015.04.017>.
- G. Melinte, O. Hosu, M. Lettieri, C. Cristea, G. Marrazza, Electrochemical fingerprint of arsenic (III) by using hybrid nanocomposite-based platforms, *Sensors* 19 (2019) 2279, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s19102279>.
- N. Elgrishi, K.J. Rountree, B.D. McCarthy, E.S. Rountree, T.T. Eisenhart, J. L. Dempsey, A practical beginner's guide to cyclic voltammetry, *J. Chem. Educ.* 95 (2018) 197–206, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.7b00361>.
- R. Rappini, A. Cincinelli, G. Marrazza, Acetamidiprid multidetection by disposable electrochemical DNA aptasensor, *Talanta* 161 (2016) 15–21, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2016.08.026>.

- [37] G. Selvolini, I. Bajan, O. Hosu, C. Cristea, R. Săndulescu, G. Marrazza, DNA-based sensor for the detection of an organophosphorus pesticide: profenofos, *Sensors* 18 (2018) 2035–2046, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s18072035>.
- [38] Z. Taleat, A. Ravalli, M. Mazloum-Ardakani, G. Marrazza, CA 125 immunosensor based on poly-anthranilic acid modified screen-printed electrodes, *Electroanalysis* 25 (2013) 269–277, <https://doi.org/10.1002/elan.201200425>.
- [39] R.-S. Saberi, S. Shahrokhian, G. Marrazza, Amplified electrochemical DNA sensor based on polyaniline film and gold nanoparticles, *Electroanalysis* 25 (2013) 1373–1380, <https://doi.org/10.1002/elan.201200434>.
- [40] X. Feng, C. Mao, G. Yang, W. Hou, J.-J. Zhu, Polyaniline/Au composite hollow spheres: synthesis, characterization, and application to the detection of dopamine, *Langmuir* 22 (2006) 4384–4389, <https://doi.org/10.1021/la053403r>.
- [41] V. Gilpin, R. McCormick, R. McMath, R.B. Smith, P. Papakonstantinou, J. Davis, Evaluating polyanthranilic acid as a polymeric template for the production of Prussian blue nanoclusters, *J. Mater. Sci.* 59 (2024) 14245–14258, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-024-10023-w>.
- [42] R. Holze, The adsorption of aniline on gold: a SERS study, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.* 250 (1988) 143–157, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0728\(88\)80199-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0728(88)80199-2).
- [43] H.K. Kordasht, M. Hasanzadeh, F. Seidi, P.M. Alizadeh, Poly (amino acids) towards sensing: recent progress and challenges, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 140 (2021) 116279, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2021.116279>.
- [44] C. Jiang, T. Yang, K. Jiao, H. Gao, A DNA electrochemical sensor with poly-l-lysine/single-walled carbon nanotubes films and its application for the highly sensitive EIS detection of PAT gene fragment and PCR amplification of NOS gene, *Electrochim. Acta* 53 (2008) 2917–2924, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2007.11.015>.
- [45] D. Zhang, L. Li, W. Ma, X. Chen, Y. Zhang, Electrodeposited reduced graphene oxide incorporating polymerization of l-lysine on electrode surface and its application in simultaneous electrochemical determination of ascorbic acid, dopamine and uric acid, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 70 (2017) 241–249, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2016.08.078>.
- [46] B. Dalkıran, P.E. Erden, C. Kaçar, E. Kılıç, Disposable amperometric biosensor based on poly-l-lysine and Fe₃O₄ NPs-chitosan composite for the detection of tyramine in cheese, *Electroanalysis* 31 (2019) 1324–1333, <https://doi.org/10.1002/elan.201900092>.
- [47] L. Simon, Z. Bognár, R.E. Gyurcsányi, Finding the optimal surface density of aptamer monolayers by SPR imaging detection-based aptamer microarrays, *Electroanalysis* 32 (2020) 851–858, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ELAN.201900736>.